

A Sociocybernetics Data Analysis Using Causality in Tourism Networks

Authors : M. Lloret-Climent, J. Nescolarde-Selva

Abstract : The aim of this paper is to propose a mathematical model to determine invariant sets, set covering, orbits and, in particular, attractors in the set of tourism variables. Analysis was carried out based on a pre-designed algorithm and applying our interpretation of chaos theory developed in the context of General Systems Theory. This article sets out the causal relationships associated with tourist flows in order to enable the formulation of appropriate strategies. Our results can be applied to numerous cases. For example, in the analysis of tourist flows, these findings can be used to determine whether the behaviour of certain groups affects that of other groups and to analyse tourist behaviour in terms of the most relevant variables. Unlike statistical analyses that merely provide information on current data, our method uses orbit analysis to forecast, if attractors are found, the behaviour of tourist variables in the immediate future.

Keywords : attractor, invariant set, tourist flows, orbits, social responsibility, tourism, tourist variables

Conference Title : ICCS 2014 : International Conference on Complex Systems

Conference Location : Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Conference Dates : August 07-08, 2014